

ENHANCED SENTIMENTAL ANALYSIS THROUGH DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEM BASED ON LEARNING TECHNIQUES USING NLTK

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, technological improvements in computing have led to the development of sophisticated decision support systems to provide support to the customers who are using social networks for getting services. In the past, certain researchers grouped product and hotel reviews into positive and negative slots, which were used to make decisions to select suitable hotels, products and services for customers and to provide guidelines to the business personalities involved in hotels. Today, people form online groups and openly discuss not only the pros - of, for instance, hotels - but also air complaints. If negative feedback is not addressed properly by hotel service providers, it will likely increase and the hotel's popularity downsized. Food served to customers depends on the preparation as well as the cost, location and times at which it is served. Further, the attitude of the sales people and hotel staff, in general, plays a key role in customers' decisions. Thus, online customer feedback through social media is useful for customer behavior analysis, crucial for the success of business. A recommendation system which addresses all these issues can provide customers better options in their choice of hotels and services.

In this proposal, two new classification algorithms are proposed. One is based on a new type of support vector machines called group support vector machines to perform major, and sub classification, of sentiments, as well as form groups based on people's sentiments with respect to changes in times and locations. The intelligent group support vector machine algorithm proposed in this thesis improves classification accuracy to provide accurate recommendations. The main advantage of the proposed work is that it helps identify people with similar interests, based on sentiments identified from tweets, and form interested groups for animated discussions on absorbing topics.

A new clustering algorithm is proposed in this research work which is useful in forming groups based on clusters. In this work, a new genetic weighted K-means clustering algorithm is proposed to detect proper cluster structures from two datasets, Twitter and Facebook. The genetic algorithm chosen here to perform clustering is an effective technique that improves classification accuracy

Keywords: NLP, Machine Learning, SVM, Sentimental Analysis

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I. INTRODUCTION

Data mining focuses on the analysis of data available in databases and data warehouses to find interesting patterns which helps to know the nature of data and its distribution. Data mining include the activities namely association rule mining, finding sequential pattern, clustering of data and classification of large volume of data sets. It also deals with outlier analysis and the advanced models like image data mining, text mining, temporal mining, spatial mining and web mining which are derived from the basic data mining techniques. Data mining techniques use the principles from statistics, rule-based systems, soft computing, databases and artificial intelligence for effective decision making in many applications. One of the important techniques in data mining is association rule mining. Moreover, sequential pattern mining is a data mining technique which applies the association rule mining techniques to infer knowledge from large databases.

The recent developments in the areas of Internet and e-commerce have become responsible for using social networks to provide reviews on products by customers. In the past, some researchers grouped the reviews into positive and negative reviews which were used to make decisions to select suitable hotels for customers and to provide guidelines to the business personalities involved in hotels (Zhongwu Zhai et al. 2012, Xu Xueke et al.2013). Very recently, people have formed online groups and discuss not only the positive qualities of hotels but also complaints. If the negative feedback is not addressed properly by the hotel service providers, their negative feedback will increase, and the popularity of the hotel will come down. The tastes of items served to the customers depend on the preparation as well as the cost, location and time at which it is served. In addition, the attitude of the salesperson and other hotel staff plays an important role in the decisions of customers (Niphath Claypo and Saichon Jaiyen 2014). Thus, online customer feedback through social media is useful for customer behavior analysis which is important for the success of businesses.

Automatic opinion mining based on social media data and customer opinions obtained through direct interaction with customers are helpful to find the most suitable restaurant and hotel for a customer. In direct interaction, either a questionnaire or feedback form can be used. Online feedback using computers, and the internet are also possible with the advent of online discussion forums. Many techniques are available in the literature, based on visualization tools (Ling Xu et al. 2008) for obtaining customer feedback. However, most customers provide their views only to their friends who can be found through face book and twitter. Therefore, the hotels must maintain a database of previous users, possible future users and customers who frequently visit restaurants and hotels. This can be obtained from travel management systems, purchase management systems and other commercial databases. An analysis of customer feedback can be used not only to recommend the hotels and services but also to improve the quality of business.

An analysis based on previous data needs techniques from Artificial Intelligence (AI), data mining, soft computing and statistics. Hence, intelligent systems which can analyze the comments from face book and twitter are necessary for effective business prediction. Moreover, questionnaires, user feedbacks and feedbacks from news papers and general public are also important to enhance the business intelligence in decision making.

Information extraction helps to extract useful information from the web pages. This is necessary because with the rapid growth of the Internet, product related word-of-mouth conversations have migrated to online markets, creating active electronic communities that provide a wealth of information. Reviewers contribute time and energy to generate reviews, enabling a social structure that provides benefits both for the users and the firms that host electronic markets. In such a context, "who" says "what" and "how" they say it, matters. On the flip side, a large number of reviews for a single product may also make it harder for individuals to track the gist of user's discussions and evaluate the truth underlying quality of a product.

Recent work has shown that the distribution of an overwhelming majority of reviews posted in online markets is bi-modal. Reviews are either allotted an extremely high rating or an extremely low rating. In such situations, the average numerical star rating assigned to a product may not convey a lot of information to a prospective buyer or to the manufacturer who tries to understand what aspects of its product are important. Instead, the reader has to read the actual reviews to examine which of the positive and which of the negative attributes of a product are of interest. Information extraction needs effective techniques for information retrieval which can be performed by carrying out feature selection and classification.

Feature selection is an activity which is aimed at picking the most important attributes from a dataset. Moreover, data preprocessing is an important component in many applications in which feature selection is one component. Feature selection can be done either at the attribute level or it can be extended upto tuple level. Through feature selection, the size of the dataset is reduced. Moreover, the redundant attributes and the attributes which do not contribute in decision making are removed. Moreover, feature selection algorithms helps to enhance the performance of the classifier by increasing the classification accuracy. Finally, the feature selection helps to reduce the training time in machine learning algorithms by reducing the number of attributes.

There are two main models that are used in feature selection namely filter methods and wrapper methods (Kohavi & John 1997). The wrapper models involve the optimization of a predictor as part of the selection process. On the other hand in filter model, the feature selection process relies on the general characteristics of the training data for selecting the important features which are independent of any predictor. The wrapper models are preferred in many applications because they provide better results in most applications than the filter model. In this work, new feature selection algorithms are proposed for selecting the most contributing features from social network data which are useful for performing sentiment classification.

Machine learning is a process of designing algorithms that can help to make production on data. machine learning can be supervised and unsupervised, machine learning process includes data initialization, learning model and testing models. the machine learning process is described in figure 1. In the data initialization, collected data is pre-processed to removal of noise then feature can be selected for better output. Learning model contain algorithms and tested data where testing model test data set for efficiency and provide expected output.

Figure 1: Machine learning process

Real-time investigation

Legacy data was structured, constrained and had limited scope. This made it easier to determine the rules. Fraud detection and prevention teams could depend on large-scale manual screening programs in which teams of people were trained to recognize patterns likely indicative of fraud when reviewing transactions.

However, with the increase in overall number of transactions and developments in real time payments, the traditional rule-based fraud detection solutions have come under pressure.

Financial institutions and merchants have only milliseconds to determine whether a transaction is genuine. Such scenarios can make legacy rule-based fraud detection ineffective, as human screeners may be likely to impose hard and fast rules on all transaction patterns. The resultant inadequate fraud scoring process bring to the fore the problem of false declines in stores or online.

Ingest large and varied data sets

Industry reports suggests that nearly 2.5 quintillion bytes of data is created everyday, with nearly 90 percent of the world's data created in last two years. Unsurprisingly, millions of transactions translates into gargantuan amounts of structured and semi-structured data like JSON and XML from different sources. Manual screening for fraud in this scenario is expensive and massively time consuming. Through Machine Learning, computers can learn from this ever-growing data. It can take the place of humans to obtain insight and help in knowledge discovery.

Machine learning is useful to improve various applications like – (i) image classification (ii) Face recognition (iii) Speech recognition (iv) Signal denoising (v) Genetics (vi) Anti spam (vii) Weather forecasting.

The Proposed work is organized as follows,

- To understand the algorithms for developing an efficient recommendation system for recommending hotels and products using sentiment analysis.
- To access new feature selection techniques from social network using soft computing techniques.
- Develop a New classification algorithm for sentiment classification and opinion mining.
- To propose new clustering technique for forming groups and to make effective decisions.
- To propose new temporal reasoning technique for predicting the customer requirements using past data, present data and temporal constraints.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Hsinchun Chen & David Zimbra (2018) Sentiment analysis and opinion mining are subareas of machine learning. They are techniques used to determine attitudes, emotions and opinions expressed by individuals on particular topics of interest. To identify relevant information and extract subjective information from source documents, sentiment analysis techniques based on opinion mining can use natural language processing (NLP) and data analytics approaches effectively. In this chapter, a survey of the related work on sentiment analysis, opinion mining, information retrieval, information extraction, feature extraction, classification and recommendation are discussed.

Mohamed AbdElhamid Abbas(2018) Deep Learning is an artificial intelligence function that imitates the mechanisms of the human mind in processing records and developing shapes to be used in selection construction. The objective of the paper is to improve the performance of the deep learning using a proposed algorithm called RFHTMC. This proposed algorithm is a merged version from Random Forest and HTM Cortical Learning Algorithm. The methodology for improving the performance of Deep Learning depends on the concept of minimizing the mean absolute percentage error which is an indication of the high performance of the forecast procedure. In addition to the overlap duty cycle which its high percentage is an indication of the speed of the processing operation of the classifier. The outcomes depict that the proposed set of rules reduces the absolute percent errors by using half of the value. And increase the percentage of the overlap duty cycle with 15%.

Siyan Chen ; Chao Peng ; Linsen Cai ; Lanying Guo(2018) The deep neural network model combining attention mechanism has achieved remarkable success in the task of target-based sentiment analysis. In current research, however, the attention mechanism is more combined with LSTM networks, such neural network- based architectures generally rely on complex computation and only focus on the single target, thus it is difficult to effectively distinguish the different polarities of variant targets in the same sentence. To address this problem, we propose a deep neural network model combining convolutional neural network and regional long short-term memory (CNN-RLSTM) for the task of target-based sentiment analysis. The approach can reduce the training time of neural network model through a regional LSTM. At the same time, the CNN-RLSTM uses a sentence-level CNN to extract sentiment features of the whole sentence, and controls the transmission of information through different weight matrices, which can effectively infer the sentiment polarities of different targets in the same sentence.

Xingfu Wang ; Jing Chen ; Ammar Hawbani ; Fuyou Miao ; Chenxi Shao(2018) In this paper, the sentiment contrast information is synonyms and antonyms of the target word, which have positive LMI score with the context word and same sentiment orientation with the target word. We integrate sentiment label information of text and sentiment contrast information into Skip-gram to distinguish such ambiguous word embedding, and build the sentiment lexicon

base on the improved word vector representation. The experiments demonstrated the effectiveness of our sentiment lexicon based on the improved word embedding, and its performance is better than the popular sentiment lexicons.

Eissa M. Alshari ; Azreen Azman ; Shyamala Doraisamy ;(2018) This paper proposed a method to enlarge the size of opinion words by learning the polarity of those non-opinion words in the vocabulary based on the SentiWordNet. The effectiveness of the method is evaluated by using the Internet Movie Review Dataset. The result is promising, showing that the proposed Senti2Vec method can be more effective than the SentiWordNet as the sentiment lexical resource.

P Ajay Rao ; B Navaneesh Kumar ; Siddharth Cadabam(2017) Deep Reinforcement Learning is the combination of Reinforcement Learning algorithms with Deep neural network, which had recent success in learning complicated unknown environments. The trained model is a Convolutional Neural Network trained using Q-Learning Loss value. The agent takes in observation, i.e. raw pixel image and reward from the environment for each step as input. The deep Q-learning algorithm gives out the optimal action for every observation and reward pair. The hyperparameters of Deep Q-Network remain unchanged for any environment. TensorFlow, an open source machine learning and numerical computation library is used to implement the deep Q-Learning algorithm on GPU.

A. Jenifer Jothi Mary ; L. Arockiam(2017) Sentiment Analysis (SA) is the study of people's opinions, emotions, and appraisals toward products and events. In the past years, it fascinated a great deal of attentions from both industry and academia for a variety of applications. Opinions are significant, because people need to make decisions. It is helpful not only for the individuals but also for the business organizations. Fuzzy logic can provide a quick way to solve the haziness present in most of the natural languages. The techniques are less explored in sentiment analysis. In this paper, Aspect based Sentiment Summarization (ASFuL) is proposed with fuzzy logic by classifying opinions polarity as strong positive, positive, negative and strong negative.

Lakshmish Kaushik ; Abhijeet Sangwan ; John H. L. Hansen(2017) A new hybrid ME-KWS joint scoring methodology is developed to model both text and audio based parameters in a single integrated formulation. For evaluation, two new databases are developed for audio based sentiment detection, namely, YouTube sentiment database and another newly developed corpus called UT-Opinion Opinion audio archive. These databases contain naturalistic opinionated audio collected in real-world conditions. The proposed solution is evaluated on audio obtained from videos in youtube.com and UT-Opinion corpus. Our experimental results show that the proposed KWS based system significantly outperforms the traditional ASR architecture in detecting sentiment for challenging practical tasks.

JunBo Xia(2016) This paper concentrates on the problem of E-commerce product recommendation, and E-commerce market has attracted more and more attentions. Collaborative filtering algorithm supposes that when two users have similar ratings on products, they may have similar preferences. To combine the user preference information and the collaborative filtering model together, we suppose that if there are two users who share the similar interest, it is very possible for them to select similar products. Afterwards, we design an E-commerce product recommendation algorithm based on collaborative filtering model to compute the recommendation score. Finally, experimental results prove that the proposed method can recommend more relevant products for users with high accuracy.

Igor N. Gluhih ; Ivan Y. Karyakin ; Lyudmila V. Sizova(2016) Recommender systems are a popular trend in recent research in Internet technologies. The models and algorithms of these systems are based on applying information of users and website content as well as their interconnections. However, there is a problem of applying these models and algorithms when the users are unidentified and there is an information gap to give recommendations. Each study

case appears as a pair of a situation and a set of possible recommendations with their characteristics.

Xiujuan Xu ; Jianyu Zhou ; Yu Liu ; (2016) Recommender systems are constructed to search the content of interest from overloaded information by acquiring useful knowledge from massive and complex data. Since the amount of information and the complexity of the data structure grow, it has become a more interesting and challenging topic to find an efficient way to process, model, and analyze the information. Due to the Global Positioning System (GPS) data recording the taxi's driving time and location, the GPS-equipped taxi can be regarded as the detector of an urban transport system. This paper proposes a Taxi-hunting Recommendation System (Taxi-RS) processing the large-scale taxi trajectory data, in order to provide passengers with a waiting time to get a taxi ride in a particular location. We formulated the data offline processing system based on HotSpotScan and Preference Trajectory Scan algorithms.

Tomomi Shibano ; Yasunari Fujimoto ; Torn Yamaguchi(2015) Recently, the number of elderly people increases in Japan, and the care prevention which let them live cheerfully is necessary. Especially, regular life and moderate exercise are important for care prevention. Today, a lot of information overflows, and a user has a burden. So, Information recommendation system is important to make the user's burden light. In this research, the authors propose the information recommendation system which supports regular life and moderate exercise by using a communication robot in the intelligent space. This system is to do the schedule management of a user and to promote exercise to the user by information recommendation.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

As the internet is growing vastly in the field of e-commerce and social networking and there is vast amount of data is to be analyzed using big data. Knowledge based sentimental analysis system is needed to make the shopping process more effective and secure in online and provide reliable preference for the users. As there is an enormous growth while performing business and customer activities through E-commerce. To analysis and predict the activities, the behavior of buyers, which able to improve the customer satisfaction and business trends. Here we have addressed the intelligent model integrated with machine learning approach to rate the customer preference with decision making process at different stages in E-commerce.

The main objective of the propose system is to give effective data searching and aggregation process to be analyze the online buyers and make their process more effectively by overcoming the more time needed for the data search and the sentimental process is to be processed more effectively. To obtain the improve confidence through fuzzy logic, which helps the data process more reliable and effective and it helps for the customer to train the system automatically through machine learning strategy with prediction. Here we have applied the association rule is performed to increase the assurance to the consumer with the help of logic model.

IV. SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

Sentiment analysis and opinion mining (Hsinchun Chen & David Zimbra 2010) are subareas of machine learning. They are techniques used to determine attitudes, emotions and opinions expressed by individuals on particular topics of interest. To identify relevant information and extract subjective information from source documents, sentiment analysis techniques based on opinion mining can use natural language processing (NLP) and data analytics approaches effectively. In this chapter, a survey of the related work on sentiment analysis, opinion mining, information retrieval, information extraction, feature extraction, classification and recommendation are discussed.

In recent years, computer users have begun using social media for communication. Therefore, user interest in topics can be identified by carrying out sentiment analysis. Many people use social networks for business, and the rise of social media has, in turn, culminated in a rise in sentiment analysis. For example, businesspeople identify new opportunities and reinforce reputations on scrutinizing reviews/ ratings available on the web. This not only matches the relevant search but also indicates relationships between words, so that both words that modify the sentiment and what the sentiment is about can be accurately identified. Certain scaling structures are also used in such systems to distinguish positive, negative and neutral sentiments.

Document level sentiment analysis (Danushka Bollegala et al. 2013) techniques described whether the whole document defines a positive or negative opinion. The main purpose of document-level sentiment analysis is to classify a document to identify its overall subjectivity and/or sentiments expressed in it. In such a case, it is possible to apply both supervised and unsupervised learning methods to perform a document-level analysis. From the literature review performed in this work, it is seen that the major advantage of performing opinion mining using sentiment analysis is that it determines the overall opinion of a particular product from a document and the disadvantage is that determining the opinion about the feature of a particular product is an impossible task in document level analysis.

In recent times, researchers have shown interest in feature selection and extraction to increase the accuracy of classification, a major challenge in opinion mining. Supervised learning methods include the hidden Markov model (Jin & Ho 2009) for classification and the conditional random field (Jakob & Gurevych 2010)-based classifications, proposed to tag features of entities. It performed well on a given specific domain but needed to be retrained when applied to different domains.

To overcome problems in supervised learning methods, unsupervised natural language processing (NLP) (Qiu et al. 2011) is proposed to extract opinion features. Here, feature extraction is performed by analyzing syntactic patterns identified from the contents of documents. It is also used to locate features, but it could not extract the invalid features because of colloquial nature of online reviews. The association rule mining (ARM) approach was proposed by Hub & Liu (2004) in which frequently showing features, also described as nouns and noun phrases are considered. The disadvantage is that invalid features are extracted incorrectly. The mutual reinforcement clustering (MRC) approach (Su et al. 2008) is developed for that very purpose. Here, the co-occurrence weight matrix is used to mine the association between features and opinion words. Even though MRC is capable of extracting infrequent features but, its precision is low because of obtaining good clusters on real life views.

Recommender systems (Adomavicius et al. 2005) tend to help people who are not with sufficient experience to evaluate the number of alternatives offered by a website. There are several techniques which were used in service recommender systems. Let us discuss some of them. Collaborative-based, content-based and knowledge-based recommendation techniques are well known. When discussing about collaborative recommendation (Schafer et al. 2007), this recommendation used to match the knowledge source of an individual with the social, which is of same type and it takes the final user preferences from his or her peers. In high-dimensional space, it uses a multi-class classification algorithm. Content-based recommendation (Balabanovic et al. 1997), however, is different. It uses certain features of items, as well as opinions of users, to train a classifier which predicts user preferences on new items. Content-based recommendation uses a binary-learning algorithm in low-dimensional space.

Finally, knowledge-based recommendation (Bridge et al. 2006) takes all types or categories in which the recommender can apply any kind of knowledge related to the domain, other than item features. It is fully dependent on inference schemes.

IV. RECOMMENDER SYSTEM

A recommender system aims to estimate the preference of a user on a new item which he has not seen. The output of a recommender system varies according to the nature of the system, its utility and information treated as inputs. It can be either a rating prediction or ranking prediction. Rating prediction aims to predict the rating scale to an item which is not seen by the user by filling the misplaced entries of the user-item rating matrix. Ranking prediction aims to predict the top n items and produces a ranked list according to its similarity with user profile or items features or both of them.

There are mainly four models used for recommendation depending on the nature of the information used as inputs. These models are content based recommender system, collaborative filtering, demographic filtering and hybrid recommendation.

Many of the modern internet services require the recommendation approaches for the perdition of new items to the user. This requirement comes from its vital role in boosting business, facilitating the decision making and tracking the user intention without his explicit intervention. Among the application fields which depend essentially on recommendation approaches are: movies recommendation, news recommendation, e-commerce services recommendation, books recommendation, e-learning recommendation, songs recommendation, websites recommendation, travel destinations recommendation, applications recommendation and so on [2].

Each recommendation scenario has its specificity for choosing entrees attributes and the suitable approaches. In the following we present some related works dealing with different applications fields.

A. Deep Collaborative Filtering Recommendation

The Deep learning is applied for enhancing collaborative filtering based recommender system. In fact, there are two most popular area of collaborative filtering which are the latent factor approaches and the neighborhood approaches. The deep learning reaches the two types of approaches. As for the latent factor approaches, the deep learning is applied for improving the performance of several algorithms such as factorization machine, matrix factorization, probabilistic matrix factorization, and K nearest neighbors' algorithm.

The selection of the deep learning technique is conditioned by the achievement of the recommendation model and its entrees parameters. Each deep learning model has its specificity which lead its integration in recommendation process. for example, the multilayer perceptron model shows its performance in modelling nonlinear interactions between user's preferences and items features which is useful for enhancing the recommendation quality. The multilayer perceptron model is integrated with the collaborative filtering to born the neural collaborative filtering techniques. The multilayer perception model is used also for solving regression and classification problems in order of enhancing the diversity as well as the accuracy of recommendation.

B. Deep Content-based Recommendation

The deep learning is applied also for content-based recommender system. In this case, the main uses of the deep learning deals with the exploitation of the advances of deep learning in thanks to the Convolutional Neural Network for visual features extraction from images and Recurrent Neural Network for extracting textual features and hence improving the recommendation quality.

The choice the appropriate neural network is conditioned by the system requirement. The convolution neural network is used in recommender systems due its performance in capturing local and global features coming from visual and textual data sources. This model is useful for solving the problem of classification and tag recommendation basing on visual features extraction from images patches or selecting informative words from textual information.

- In this proposal, a new recommendation system is proposed to provide functional services to social network users through the application of new techniques for data pre-processing and classification.
- This system also uses intelligent rules for competent decision making. In this proposal, a two-level filtering approach is adopted to choose a set of reviews, perceived by customers to be useful.
- The filtering process is based on the concept that reviewer-generated textual content and other characteristics of a review influence peer customers making apposite purchasing choices.
- The filtered reviews are processed to obtain a relative sentiment score associated with each of the product's features discussed in the reviews. Based on these scores, the customer's impression of each of the product's features can be judged and used for the benefit of manufacturers.

VII. MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES FOR SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

The social networking sites dispense their data conveniently and freely on the web. This availability of data entices the interest of young researchers to plunge them in the field of sentiment analysis. People express their emotions and perspectives on the social media discussion forums [6]. The business organizations employ researchers to investigate the unrevealed facts about their products and services. Spontaneous and automatic determination of sentiments from reviews is the main concern of multinational organizations . The machine learning techniques have improved accuracy of sentiment analysis and expedite automatic evaluation of data these days. This work attempted to utilize four machine learning techniques for the task of sentiment analysis. The modeling of four techniques is briefly discussed below.

A. Naïve Bayes used for sentiment classification

The dichotomy of sentiment is generally decided by the mindset of an author of text whether he is positively or negatively oriented towards his saying. Naïve Bayes classifier is a popular supervised classifier, furnishes a way to express positive, negative and neutral feelings in the web text. Naïve Bayes classifier utilizes conditional probability to classify words into their respective categories. The benefit of using Naïve Bayes on text classification is that it needs small dataset for training. The raw data from web undergoes preprocessing, removal of numeric, foreign words, html tags and special symbols yielding the set of words. The tagging of words with labels of positive, negative and neutral tags is manually performed by human experts.

B. J48 algorithm used for sentiment prediction

The hierarchical mechanism divides feature space into distinct regions followed by the categorization of sample into category labels. J48 is a decision tree based classifier used to generate rules for the prediction of target terms. It has an ability to deal with larger training datasets than other classifiers [14]. The word features for sentences of corpus taken from labeled arff file of training set are represented in the leaf nodes of decision tree. In the test set every

time when a near feature qualifies the label condition of internal feature node, its level is lifted up in the same branch of decision tree. The assignment of labels to the word features of test set gradually generates different two branches of decision tree.

C. BFTREE algorithm used for sentiment prediction

Another classification approach outperforms J48, C4.5 and CART by expanding only best node in the depth first order. BFTree algorithm excavates the training file for locating best supporting matches of positive and negative terms in the test file. BFTree algorithm keeps heuristic information gain to identify best node by probing all collected word features. The only difference between J48 and BFTree classifier is the computation order in which decision tree is built.

D. CLASSIFICATION

In this work, new techniques are proposed for feature selection and sentiment analysis using classification algorithms. For this purpose, tweets are collected from 5000 users for a period of one month. This work considered sentiments - such as happiness, joy, sadness, anger, fear, surprise, distress and disgust - and identified the words used to express them. Based on an analysis of synonyms, we select features for positive and negative sentiments with the proposal of a new feature reduction (selection) algorithm using keyword frequency and semantic analysis. Moreover, a new classification algorithm is proposed based on a new type of support vector machine called Group Support Vector Machines (GSVMs)[26] to perform major as well as sub classification of sentiments, and form groups based on people's sentiments with respect to changes in times and locations. Finally, the groups are used to form discussion forums on diverse topics including business, tours, elearning, religion and sports. The key advantage of the proposed work is to identify people with similar interests, based on sentiments identified from tweets, and form interest groups for discussions on interesting topics.

Moreover, in a hotel recommendation system Spatio-temporal constraints play a major role in decision making. Temporal constraints are useful for performing temporal reasoning tasks such as prediction, planning and learning (Kannan & Geetha 1998). Artificial neural network (ANN) or simply neural network (NN) (Haykin 1998) is a popular data modeling tool that can perform intelligent tasks similar to the human brain. NN is well-known for high precision and high learning ability even when a very little information is available. One of the reliable methods of data classification from the neural network domain is the Multilayer Perceptron Back propagation network (MLPBPN) (Werbos 1994) algorithm. Due to the presence of imprecise input information, ambiguity or vagueness in input data, overlapping boundaries among classes, and indefiniteness in defining features some uncertainties can still arise at any stage of a data classification system. The fuzzy set theory (Zadeh 1965; Dubois & Prade 1990) as a generalization of the classical set theory is very flexible in handling different aspects of uncertainties or incompleteness about real life situations. In a fuzzy system the features are associated with a degree of membership to different classes. Both NNs and fuzzy systems are very convenient in estimating the input-output relationships. Neural networks deal with numeric and quantitative data while fuzzy systems can handle symbolic and qualitative data. Neuro-fuzzy hybridization leads to a crossbreed intelligent system widely known as Neuro-fuzzy system (NFS) (Jang et al. 1997) that exploits the best qualities of these two approaches efficiently.

There is another Neuro-fuzzy classification based model which comprises a set of interpretable IF-THEN rules. Moreover, fuzzy rules can be extended with temporal constraints in the form of Neuro-fuzzy temporal rules (Ganapathy et al. 2014) for making effective decisions. Along

with, the introduction of spatial constraints is very useful for making effective decisions depends on location.

In this work, a new recommendation system is proposed for recommending suitable hotels using soft computing techniques. This new Hotel Recommendation System is mainly for the customers who consider their taste, requirements with respect to time, place and economic status. We analyze the users taste from huge number of customers by collecting their opinions from online reviews and also by using the proposed questionnaire. The proposed system has been built using text mining techniques that also consider uncertainty for faithfully modelling and analyzing customer opinions and are recommended to different variety of hotels and restaurants. For the purpose, a new feature selection algorithm is proposed in this thesis for extracting useful opinions which are used to form users groups for recommending the suitable hotels to them. In addition, this work uses a feature grouping method for recommending hotels based on ranking. Finally, a new Neuro-fuzzy classification algorithm is proposed in this thesis for categorizing the user's opinions to make necessary and suitable decisions over the users.

E. System Architecture

Figure 2 shows the architecture of the proposed system discussed in this thesis. It consists of eight components: a user interface, query and document analyzer, decision manager, feature selection module, classification module, document manager, document database and lookup database. A user can interact with the system through the user interface. The query given by the user is given to the query analyzer. The query analyzer searches the twitter for user discussions based on the query. The discussions are analyzed and stored in the document database [31]. The overall control of the system is with the decision manager. The feature selection module is responsible for forming features. The classification module classifies documents and submits them to the decision manager, which uses the classified results and lookup table to decide on the formation of groups. After forming groups, the decision manager informs the user interface through the document manager. The last is responsible for managing discussions by group members as well as their profiles.

Figure 2 System Architecture

The sentimental analysis is a Natural Language processing (NLP), which extract the resource from the emotional text are in the form of raw data. The sentimental analysis is nothing but the mining process, which can extract the emotional text with right or wrong one and results in sentiment score. As this sentimental is usually done for certain real time applications such as, reviews of social media, hotel, etc. As in this work, we have considered the hotel review to be more effective based on extraction of emotion using machine, which can read those emotions from learning. As this machine learning will read those review related to hotel information's and extract those useful information's are used to build the effective resource and improve the development of the particular sector.

In this emotional text, which is classes into three as positive, negative and neutral. By considering the hotel review, the customer feedback plays a vital role for the development of the hotel. The sentimental analysis can automate the process of determining the hotel structure and customer based on review of three classes. Here the customer review will be segregated into review, feedback, rating, comments, attached replies and smiley emoji. Based on the review text that can be segregated into positive, negative and neutral class, which uses parsing the data extracted and data stemming uses to reduce the words from certain word of root and it is

essential for NLU (Natural Language Understanding) and NLP. Then finally tokenization, which is nothing but the breaking the text into small unit of token i.e. similar to divide and conquer concept. Then the above rules are set and then moved into set of words comparison to categories the review.

- a. Building a word cloud or topic modelling model to identify what are the key reasons for people to love this hotel.

It is used as a performance on feedback indicator using modified sentimental analysis like naive, bayesian, etc. which are existing before which can encode each word to be positive or negative and then repeat the process to cover the entire text to count positive words as well as negative words and then also added neutral and compound as correlation ratio. In this sentimental analysis, we will be considering more functionalities like sadness, joy, stress, trust, etc

- b. Comparing the sentiment scores with other hotels by extracting the reviews from other hotels and analysing with the above steps.

Here we counts the frequency of words and resizes each word based on their frequencies i.e., more outstanding. Here we can use name-based entity recognition. Which uses This code snippet scans a text sentence by sentence and labels each word if the word is recognized as "entity" and combine the named entity with sentiment analysis/word cloud.

Word cloud library can be added using pip command, which can read the data file (.csv file) and store in into a Pandas DataFrame. Word cloud generation helps to generate the word cloud using the Word Cloud function.

- c. Extracting more information like review dates, reviewers' contributions, reviewers' helpful votes, review helpful votes, the number of shares, etc, visualize them and apply business analysis approaches.

Analyses can be made for both word-level and sentence-level analyses, which can cover all the content with entire segment by summarizing the sentence by calculating the count the frequency of each word and rank sentences i.e., highest word frequency (Latent Dirichlet Allocation exists so far). Here we can extract the information by using machine learning like convolutional or rational by one-hot encoding representations enabled with enables non-orthogonal relationships to produce the producing a well-organized sentence.

For extracting the web-based content, we use web scrapping tool to extract from the enormous amount of data.

To perform the sentimental analysis,

1. Data Collection.
2. Data Preparation.
3. Sentimental detection
4. Classification of sentimental
5. Data presentation

For the data preparation, pre-processing will be initiated with large number of dataset with certain components as mentioned below,

1. Case Folding
2. Removal
3. Lemma Generation
4. Token Generation
5. Feature Extraction
6. Feature Selection

7. Feature Representation

VIII. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Here in this sentimental analysis, we have applied with python language with defined libraries where we can apply machine learning and NLP into it.

Here we have used **Scikit learn**, where we can apply machine learning to learn the data used for the process of extraction like SVM, random forest, K means, etc.

To organize the data that are taken into structuring those data, then manipulating those and make then into tabular form of data to process. (**Panda module**)

NLTK (Natural Language ToolKit) module is used to pre process the data made for natural processing based on the data obtained from the machine learning information. As we have applied NLTK, we can import the naive Bayesian classifier to analyse the sentimental review where we have used text frequency concept with document frequency also.

After the analyse have been done, data are processed to determine the division and dissimilarity score and can be process by **TextBlob and Numpy** used for certain data, which can be manipulated and compute for the process of data analyse.

For analysis the data based on machine learning technique, determine the compare two words and can be shared that can represent the same context. Here we gone for unsupervised learning to learn the data and then sort those frequent words, which is specific to positive/negative/neutral category. Then finally we calculate the division score where we can use TextBlob module for Python.

Then we can use classification of text / words where we can apply naive bayes along with NLTK module in python. The bayes rule can be applied into the document where we can have maximum posterior value to represent the document features.

For extracting the web-based content, we use web scrapping tool to extract from the enormous amount of data.

In the performance analysis, the effectiveness can be determined based on the number of images deliberated. The TensorFlow deployed with specific modules as learning rate scheduler, checkpoint. Kaggle dataset contains specific attributes such as patient, RNSseq cluster, laterality, tumor location, and ethnicity. Then those datasets contain images and perform sorting the data with checkpoint and lead to final datasets. The final dataset contains patient id, image path and mask path as mentioned in Table 1. To determine the mask count plot by comparing the count value and mask.

Table. 1 Mask Count Part

S.No.	Mask	Dtype
1	0	2556
2	1	1373

The brain tumor images are varied based on the pixel colour to identify the position of the tumor on mask value. Then new dataset is created based on the variables such as image_path,

mask_path and mask. Based on the model selection, trained data are tested and separated based on brain_df_train, test_size = 0.15. Then those images are validated.

The images are trained based on the classifier model concerning to Residual Network ResNet50 is being used. The input layer performs image classification on Conv2D, Input, ZeroPadding2D, Batch Normalization, Activation, MaxPooling2D, batch normalization images. The classifier model obtained a data loss of 0.2353 and a data accuracy of 94.745% based on the image classification model to detect whether the tumor exists or not. The accuracy_score, confusion_matrix, and classification_report metrics create the confusion matrix based on original and prediction images as represented in Table. 2 and 3.

Table. 2. Attribute metrics based on mask value

Mask_Value	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
0	0.93	0.99	0.96	382
1	0.98	0.87	0.92	208

Table. 3. Attribute metrics based on mask value (Accuracy; Macro Avg; Weighted Avg)

Mask_Value	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Accuracy	-	-	0.95	590
Macro Avg	0.96	0.93	0.94	590
Weighted Avg	0.95	0.95	0.95	590

Then the proposed image segmentation model Residual U-Net is deployed to identify the tumor location as the train data size is 1167.

In data block creation, batch size is considered to determine the image ID and mask ID. Based on each epoch, the data indices get updated. The Residual data block is created by resblock(X, f) based on Conv2D, batch normalization and activation function. The image segmentation model trains the image datasets based on the custom loss function for the ResUNet model. In the loss function, cross entropy is used with epsilon and smooth value.

Figure 3. Epochs Vs Focal Tverskyloss

In Figure. 3, focal tversky loss is determined for propose Res U-Net architecture based on the epochs varies from 0 to 50.

In Figure. 4, Tversky Accuracy is determined for the proposed Residual U-Net architecture based on the epoch varies from 0 to 50 for the trained data and val. There is a gradual increase in the Accuracy as there is an increase in the epochs.

Figure 4. Epochs Vs Tversky Accuracy

In Figure. 5, the loss is calculated based on the classification model by varying the epochs from 0 to 30. The loss gets saturated as the epochs increase in the value for the proposed Res U-Net.

Enhanced Sentimental Analysis through Decision Support System based on Learning Techniques Using NLTK

Figure 5. Epochs Vs Loss

The Accuracy is calculated and increases based on the increase in the epochs value, which varies from 0 to 30. It is represented in Fig, 6.

Fig 6. Epochs Vs Accuracy

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